

ACCURACY ANALYSIS OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL MODEL RECONSTRUCTED BY SPHERICAL VIDEO IMAGES

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ABSTRACT: Indoor 3D model is useful for navigation purpose and virtual reality applications. However, its surface is usually texture-less with unbalanced illumination situations together with complex architecture design, which is difficult to acquire images and produce the high-quality 3D model. In this study, we propose the use of spherical video images due to its 720 degrees field-of-view (FOV) and its sequential data acquisition is friendly to the user. In order to evaluate its performance, positioning accuracy and feasibility, we also acquire terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) data for comparison and measure ground control points (GCPs) by a total station for accuracy analysis. The Garmin VIRB 360 spherical camera is used to acquire video at 30 fps (frame per second) with an image size of 3840 x 2178. The video is converted to static image sequence with a time interval of 1.23 seconds. The stitched spherical images were imported into Agisoft Photoscan Pro for 3D modeling. The photo triangulation is conducted by Structure-from-Motion (SfM) technique and the positioning accuracy was assessed by GCPs within the Photoscan Pro software. Later, a dense point cloud, mesh model as well as photo-realistic texture model can be produced. The produced dense point cloud was compared with TLS data within CloudCompare software. The experiment result shown that the 3D positioning accuracy (RMSE) after SfM is about 18.9 cm, while the 3D distance discrepancy between the produced dense point cloud with TLS data is about 40.3 cm. The major problem that causes such a large error is the stitching algorithm to create a spherical image does not follow the photogrammetric collinearity condition. It demonstrates that the adoption of Garmin VIRB 360 spherical camera for 3D modeling is beneficial in data acquisition, but its positioning accuracy is too low for high-accuracy applications and may be applicable to indoor navigation applications.

KEYWORDS: 3D model reconstruction, Spherical Image, Close-Range Photogrammetry, Terrestrial Laser Scanning.

1. INTRODUCTION

The interest in spherical images as a source to indoor building documentation has been increased. Several approaches have permitted to generate geometries and 3D model based on spherical photogrammetry (Ramos, 2016). Thus, the metric effectiveness of spherical images has been validated and the use of these images within virtual environments has already widespread. The indoor is a complex environment for three-dimensional model reconstruction using imaging techniques due to its unbalanced illumination and architecture design. However, indoor 3D model is useful for navigation purpose and virtual reality applications.

In this paper, the spherical image is obtained using videogrammetry and its sequential data acquisition is friendly to the user. Videogrammetry is a measurement technique that is mainly based on the principles of photogrammetry [2]. Videogrammetry refers to video images taken using a camcorder or movie function on digital still camera. Video movie consists of sequences of images (or frames).

Spherical video images has a FOV of 720 degrees. A rotating line spherical camera takes the spherical image and a camera calibration method based on perpendicular panels covered by checkerboard patterns was proposed for estimating the projection parameters and recovering the camera pose (Guan, 2011).

The motivation for this paper is to evaluate the performance of 3D model reconstruction from a spherical video camera, including its positioning accuracy and feasibility. Thus, we also acquire TLS data for comparison and measure several GCPs and independent check points by a total station for accuracy analysis.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the software used for three-dimensional models reconstruction is Agisoft Photoscan Professional and an open source CloudCompare software is used for point clouds comparison and mesh processing.

In general, there are five steps to reconstruct a 3D model from spherical video image. The first step is to acquire video image using the Garmin VIRB360 video camera. Its specification is shown in Table 1. Then, we extract spherical images from the video to obtain the spherical video images in equal-rectangular projection. The second step is the initial processing for aerial triangulation with camera self-calibration. In the meantime, we mark several GCPs and independent check points measured by a total station for control and accuracy analysis. Later, we conduct dense image matching, i.e. the fourth step, to obtain dense point cloud with real dimension. For overall performance assessment, we utilize Riegl VZ400 TLS to collect reference point cloud. In the end, we compare their 3D discrepancy. Figure 1 is a research workflow that describes the steps of the research process.

Table 1. Specification of GARMIN VIRB 360 video camera

Sensor type	CMOS
No of cameras	Two
Video resolution	3840 x 2178
Image Format	Stitched image from spherical cameras in equal-rectangular projection.
FPS (frame per second)	30
Video format	MP4 (AVC / H.264 Encoding)

Figure 1. Research workflow

3. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

3.1 Data Acquisition

The test-site of this research is located at the Geomatics Building, National Cheng Kung University, Taiwan. The total number of images used in this study is 134. Figure 2 is an example of spherical video image obtained from the video sequence. It shows that the spherical image has a horizontal FOV of 360 degrees and vertical FOV with 180 degrees. Each spherical image was stitched by its front and rear camera images. The video is converted to static image sequence with a time interval of 1.23 seconds.

RIEGL VZ-400 TLS is used to collect reference point cloud. RIEGL VZ-400 is a terrestrial laser scanner that has a 1.5 m minimum scan range. Its laser wavelength is near infrared, together with 5 mm measurement accuracy and 3 mm measurement precision. The final reference point cloud data was registered from three TLS stations to minimize occlusion effect. The standard deviation of registration error is about 1.8 mm. For completeness purpose, the TLS position for scanning should include all

the sections on the object of the indoor. The registered TLS reference point cloud is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Spherical video images

Figure 3. TLS point cloud

3.2 Aerial Triangulation and Dense Point Cloud Generation

In PhotosanPro, the aerial triangulation was conducted by using SfM techniques. After feature point detection and tie-point matching the location and orientation of all spherical images can be calculated. This process also generates a sparse 3D point cloud that includes all the portions of the object acquired during the image acquisition, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Sparse point cloud with camera location

In order to compare the final result with TLS point cloud, we have to mark GCPs with same coordinates system as the TLS data. Further, we may evaluate the overall triangulation accuracy using the check points. If its accuracy is acceptable. Then, the number of cloud points can be increased by using a dense image matching technique, the result is called dense cloud point. Figure 5 shows the dense point cloud with more geometrical details.

Figure 5. Dense point cloud

Finally, 3D meshing and generic texture rendering method were applied, which allows parameterization of texture atlas for arbitrary geometry and make a final 3D textured model of the study site. It gives a photo-realistic representation of a scene. As shown in figure 6, there are some outlier points appear at the boundary of object due to larger surface curvature and discontinuity. The result of point clouds was also affected by several factors such as the illumination condition of the indoor environment may too dark at some corners. Meanwhile, the windows were made of glass, so the generated point cloud is noisy and most of them are blunder, so most of them have been removed from the figure.

Figure 6. The 3D texture model is very noisy

To perform quantitative evaluation, we use CloudCompare software to get distance between the TLS point cloud and the point cloud generated by the spherical video image.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Evaluation of the image geo-referencing

The evaluation of the metric accuracy achieved with the equal-rectangular projections of the Garmin VIRB 360 was carried out with a set of check points measured with a

total station. There are 29 targets placed around study site and were measured with a total station (the expected accuracy is ± 3 cm). Figure 7 and 8 shows the distribution of the reference points, whereas the resulting metric results are shown in table 2.

Figure 7. Reference point well distributed at the full frame of the image

Images were acquired indoor, so that a uniform illumination may not easily achieved. Illumination conditions are an important issue for images acquired under an angle of 360° . Although the camera allows one to control some parameters for image acquisition, it is rather difficult to guarantee a uniform illumination in real projects where the full 360° scenes are captured. The software used for photogrammetric processing is Agisoft PhotoScan Pro, which support spherical camera model and suitable for spherical photogrammetric applications.

Figure 8 Reference point located in the middle portion of the image

Figure 9. The distance between photogrammetric point cloud and TLS point cloud

Table 2. The statistics for control points and checkpoints with the spherical projections generated with different case studies. (unit: cm)

Reference point well distributed at the full frame of the image			
	horizontal errors	vertical errors	reprojection errors
No. of GCPs = 6	4.274	4.520	8.536
No. of Check Points = 23	12.070	11.604	31.489

Reference point located in the middle portion of the image			
	horizontal errors	vertical errors	reprojection errors
No. of GCPs = 7	3.031	3.824	6.606
No. of Check Points = 15	6.822	6.742	21.436

The results with the proposed calibration procedure on the middle portion of the image are better than those achieved with the distributed point at the full frame of the image. One reason that the accuracy is so low is because the stitching process doesn't project the original image to a virtual sphere well. At the middle of the image, the projection is better than at the top and bottom portion of the spherical image.

4.2 Accuracy assessment of a point cloud

In order to compare spherical and TLS point clouds, the point clouds must be register to each other. Since both point clouds contain outliers, first we start with eliminating the outliers and leave only the points of interested in the generated point cloud. The resulting point cloud number is show in table 3. The number of points might increase if more input images are used. However, that also leads to higher computation time and memory requirements.

Table 3. The matching results	
Sparse Point Cloud	66,053
Dense Point Cloud	4,063,465
TLS Point Cloud	56,281,574

Table 4. Statistics of distance computation (unit: cm)

Max Distance	25.71
Average Distance	3.47
Max Error	0.76
RMS	0.46
Standard Deviation	3.76

CONCLUSIONS

The geometric detail and accuracy of point clouds generated from VIRB 360 spherical video images is too low for high-accuracy applications. Several factors affect the accuracy and details are spherical camera calibration, spherical image stitching algorithm, image resolution, object material and the variability of illumination conditions in the rooms. The major problem that causes such a large error is the stitching algorithm to create a spherical image that does not fit the photogrammetric collinearity condition. It is particularly, the reference point located in the middle of the portion of the image has better accuracy than reference points well distributed at the full frame of the image. Nevertheless, the generated 3D model still can be applied to many applications, such as navigation within an indoor of a building.

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